

VARIABLE STIFFNESS FLEXIBLE MATRIX LAMINATES WITH PRESCRIBED FINITE ELASTIC DEFORMATION

C.S. Sousa^{1*}, P.P. Camanho², F.M. Andrade Pires², A. Suleman¹

¹ Mechanical Engineering Department, University of Victoria, 3800 Finnerty Road, Victoria BC V8P 5C2, Canada, ² DEMec, Faculdade de Engenharia, Universidade do Porto, Rua Dr. Roberto Frias, 4200-465, Porto, Portugal

* Corresponding author (carlos.santos.sousa@fe.up.pt)

keywords: *variable stiffness plates, nonlinear deformation, flexible composites*

1. Introduction

Flexible matrix composites (FMCs) are materials that combine stiff fibers in soft matrices. Unidirectional FMC laminates are highly anisotropic since the ratio between longitudinal and transverse elastic modulus is usually much higher than conventional rigid polymer matrix laminates. Thus, the stiffness of the laminate changes significantly when the orientation of the fiber varies from a parallel to a perpendicular direction with respect to the load. Fiber reinforced rubber material are examples of flexible matrix composites.

A higher level of anisotropy is introduced when combining the constitutive properties of FMC laminates with the curvilinear fiber trajectories of variable stiffness composite panels. The main reason is that the interaction between the curved fibers may increase the coupling between shearing and stretching. The result is a flexible laminate with an advanced stiffness tailoring capability. Composite plates with a central hole subjected to in-plane loading is an example of a typical application for the variable stiffness design concept since it allows for an optimized modification of the highly non-uniform stress distribution induced by the hole [1, 2].

Luo [3] investigated on flexible matrix composites with both continuous straight fibers and wavy fibers in an elastic matrix and flexible composites reinforced by plain-weave fabrics under biaxial loading. For the straight fiber case a Kevlar/Silicon elastomer laminate was used for testing. The theoretical model was in good agreement with the experimental results except for specimens with fibers at 85% after 60% strain.

A potential application for this type of material may be envisaged in aerospace shape-adaptable or morphing structures like wing skins or aerodynamic fairings that require significant elastic deformation in order to extend the flight envelope or improve the overall performance of the aircraft.

To accurately predict the stress and strain fields of such structures a different formulation than that of conventional linear elastic theory based on infinitesimal strain assumption is required. In this paper a finite elastic theory is adopted to model the deformed configuration of the flexible variable stiffness laminate relative to the undeformed configuration. A Lagrangian description of the constitutive relations is derived based on a fourth order strain-energy function. The deformation of a typical variable stiffness plate is then prescribed with a motion law that accounts for simple shear superposed with simple extension.

The purpose of this paper is to derive the nonlinear elastic relations of flat rectangular composite laminates combining a flexible matrix with variable stiffness properties under imposed deformation.

2. Notation and General Theory

The analysis of the finite deformation of the lamina is based on the relation between the initial or undeformed body and the final or deformed body, denoted by $\hat{\mathcal{K}}$ and \mathcal{K} , respectively. The following exposition of the theory assumes a two-dimensional space and therefore an in-plane deformation.

Referring to Fig. 1, an arbitrary point P inside the lamina may be measured in two distinct vector spaces. The first is called the material or mathematical space, where the position of point P is measured by the Lagrangian coordinates X^1 and X^2 . These coordinates are associated with a Cartesian frame defined by an origin O' and two mutually orthogonal basis vectors \mathbf{e}'_1 and \mathbf{e}'_2 .

The second is called the physical or spacial space. Similarly, a Cartesian frame with origin O , orthogonal basis vectors \mathbf{e}_1 and \mathbf{e}_2 and associated Eulerian coordinates x^1 and x^2 is introduced.

The material and physical spaces are related by a mapping Φ such that at a given time t ,

$$\mathbf{x} = \Phi(\mathbf{X}, t) \tag{1}$$

where $\mathbf{x} = x^1\mathbf{e}_1 + x^2\mathbf{e}_2$ and $\mathbf{X} = X^1\mathbf{e}'_1 + X^2\mathbf{e}'_2$. The initial configuration is obtained at time $t = 0$, and relation (1) takes the following notation:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \dot{\Phi}(\mathbf{X}) \tag{2}$$

where $\dot{\Phi} \equiv \Phi(\mathbf{X}, 0)$.

Figure 1: Relationship between the Material and Physical Spaces.

It is assumed that the initial and deformed configurations are related by a linear mapping \mathcal{T} such that,

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathcal{T}(\dot{\mathbf{x}}, t). \tag{3}$$

Combining equations (1), (2) and (3) it follows that

$$\Phi(\mathbf{X}, t) = \mathcal{T}(\dot{\Phi}(\mathbf{X}), t). \tag{4}$$

The deformation gradient tensor is denoted by \mathbf{F} and is defined by

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{x}_j \dot{\mathbf{x}}^j \tag{5}$$

where the Einstein summation convention applies. The vectors $\dot{\mathbf{x}}_i$ and \mathbf{x}_i form local bases in \mathcal{K} and \mathcal{K} , respectively, and are given by

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_i = \frac{\partial \dot{\mathbf{x}}}{\partial X^i} \tag{6a}$$

$$\mathbf{x}_i = \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial X^i} \tag{6b}$$

For the Cartesian coordinate system $O\mathbf{e}_i$ the deformation gradient takes the form

$$\mathbf{F} = \frac{\partial x^i}{\partial \dot{x}^j} \mathbf{e}_i \mathbf{e}^j \tag{7}$$

The Green-Lagrange strain tensor is defined by

$$\mathbf{E} = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{C} - \mathbf{I}) \tag{8}$$

where

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{F}^T \cdot \mathbf{F} \tag{9}$$

is the right Cauchy-Green deformation tensor and \mathbf{I} is the identity tensor.

3. Curvilinear Fiber Path Definition

Consider a rectangular flat composite lamina with length ℓ , width w and thickness h . It is composed of a single family of curved fibers that are distributed parallel to each other along the plane of the lamina [4–6], as shown in Fig. 2. The lamina is considered to be a continuum body, or an assemblage of material particles and the fibers are assumed to be described by a continuous vector field. As a simplifying assumption, only the centreline of the actual tow path is considered in the analysis. The layout adopted for the fiber distribution is obtained from the shifted method presented in [7].

Since in this case both the material and the physical spaces are orthonormal Cartesian spaces, it is usual to set $\overset{\circ}{\Phi}$ to the identity mapping,

$$\overset{\circ}{\Phi}(\mathbf{X}) = \mathbf{X}. \quad (10)$$

which from (2) implies $\overset{\circ}{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{X}$ and from (4) results in the relation $\Phi(\mathbf{X}, t) = \mathcal{T}(\overset{\circ}{\mathbf{x}}, t)$. Also, it is assumed that the deformed configuration is measured at a fixed time instant and so the dependency on t will be omitted in the following derivations.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of a general ply.

The general equation for the curvilinear trajectory of a reference fiber in the undeformed configuration is given in [8] and may be rewritten in the form

$$\hat{x}^1 = r \cos \phi - \tilde{g}(r) \sin \phi + \hat{x}_0^1 \quad (11a)$$

$$\hat{x}^2 = r \sin \phi + \tilde{g}(r) \cos \phi + \hat{x}_0^2 \quad (11b)$$

where r is the distance measured along the fiber reference axis and ϕ is the angle between the x^1 direction and that axis. The reference fiber is represented in Fig. 2 as a red stroked curved path.

The function \tilde{g} is continuous and periodic in the r direction with period $2D$, and is defined as

$$\tilde{g}(r) = (g \circ f_1)(r) - 2f_2(r)g(-D) \quad (12)$$

where the notation $g \circ f_1$ denotes the composition of functions g with f_1 . Function f_1 denotes the sawtooth wave function with both period and peak-to-peak amplitude of $2D$. This function is plotted in Fig. 3 and may be cast in the form

$$f_1(r) = r - 2Df_2(r) \quad (13)$$

and

$$f_2(r) = \left\lfloor \frac{r}{2D} + \frac{1}{2} \right\rfloor \quad (14)$$

where $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ represents the floor operator defined by

$$\lfloor x \rfloor = \max\{m \in \mathbb{Z} \mid m \leq x\}.$$

 Figure 3: The sawtooth wave function, f_1 .

The function g is defined by

$$g(r) = \begin{cases} -\frac{D}{T_1 - T_0} \log \frac{\cos \psi(r)}{\cos(T_0)} & \text{if } 0 \leq r < D, \\ \frac{D}{T_1 - T_0} \log \frac{\cos \psi(r)}{\cos(T_0)} & \text{if } -D \leq r < 0 \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

where ψ denotes the fiber orientation angle and is given by

$$\psi(r) = \begin{cases} T_0 + (T_1 - T_0) \frac{r}{D} & \text{if } 0 \leq r < D, \\ T_0 - (T_1 - T_0) \frac{r}{D} & \text{if } -D \leq r < 0 \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

where the parameters T_0 and T_1 are the fiber orientation angles at $r = 0$ and $r = D$, respectively.

4. Material Frame and Material Basis Vectors

Considering the lamina represented in Fig. 2, a local material frame is defined at every point P in the domain. This frame is defined by two basis vectors in the undeformed configuration denoted by $\hat{\mathbf{m}}_1$ and $\hat{\mathbf{m}}_2$. Vector $\hat{\mathbf{m}}_1$ is always parallel to the tangential direction of the fiber at P and directs to increasing r , and vector $\hat{\mathbf{m}}_2$ is parallel to the fiber shift direction.

As the fibers undergo the deformation associated with \mathbf{F} , they are convected with the material which results in a transformation of the material frame given by

$$\mathbf{m}_i = \mathbf{F} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{m}}_i \quad (17)$$

for $i = 1, 2$. In general, the angle between the basis vectors is changed as the lamina is being deformed. Since this is a two-dimensional deformation, no bending or twisting of the fibers is taken into account.

One way to derive the expressions for the material basis vectors in terms of the fiber path parameters is to associate the local material frame with a curvilinear coordinate system defined by equations (11). Since this system of equations is limited to the reference fiber path, a new parameter, s , is introduced that describes the offset of the actual fiber containing P with respect to the reference fiber. This offset is measured along the shift direction. Thus, equations (11) becomes

$$\dot{x}^1 = r \cos \phi - (\tilde{g}(r) + s) \sin \phi + \dot{x}_0^1, \quad (18a)$$

$$\dot{x}^2 = r \sin \phi + (\tilde{g}(r) + s) \cos \phi + \dot{x}_0^2. \quad (18b)$$

This set of equations may be viewed as an affine transformation and may be written succinctly as

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{R}_\phi \cdot \mathbf{y} + \dot{\mathbf{x}}_0 \quad (19)$$

where \mathbf{R}_ϕ is the rotation tensor representing a counterclockwise rotation by the angle ϕ . The rotation tensor will be defined in the next section. The vectors \mathbf{y} and $\dot{\mathbf{x}}_0$ are defined by

$$\mathbf{y}(r, s) = r\mathbf{e}_1 + (\tilde{g}(r) + s)\mathbf{e}_2 \quad (20)$$

and

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_0 = \dot{x}_0^1\mathbf{e}_1 + \dot{x}_0^2\mathbf{e}_2 \quad (21)$$

respectively.

For a fixed angle ϕ , the material basis vectors may then be given by

$$\dot{\mathbf{m}}_1 = \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial r} = \mathbf{R}_\phi \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial r}, \quad (22a)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{m}}_2 = \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial s} = \mathbf{R}_\phi \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial s}. \quad (22b)$$

Equation (22a) involves the derivative of \tilde{g} , which in turn is defined in (12). The function \tilde{g} is continuous and differentiable and its derivative is given by

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{g}}{\partial r} = \tan(\psi \circ f_1). \quad (23)$$

Introducing the vectors \mathbf{y}_r and \mathbf{y}_s , the partial derivatives of \mathbf{y} may be expressed by

$$\mathbf{y}_r \equiv \frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial r} = \mathbf{e}_1 + \tan(\psi \circ f_1)\mathbf{e}_2 \quad (24a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}_s \equiv \frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial s} = \mathbf{e}_2 \quad (24b)$$

The normalized material basis vectors with respect to the undeformed configuration are denoted by $\mathring{\mathbf{a}}_1$ and $\mathring{\mathbf{a}}_2$ and may be obtained from $\dot{\mathbf{m}}_1$ and $\dot{\mathbf{m}}_2$ respectively,

$$\mathring{\mathbf{a}}_1 \equiv \frac{\dot{\mathbf{m}}_1}{\|\dot{\mathbf{m}}_1\|} = \mathbf{R}_\phi \cdot \frac{\mathbf{y}_r}{\|\mathbf{y}_r\|} = \cos(\psi \circ f_1)\mathbf{R}_\phi \cdot \mathbf{y}_r \quad (25a)$$

$$\mathring{\mathbf{a}}_2 \equiv \frac{\dot{\mathbf{m}}_2}{\|\dot{\mathbf{m}}_2\|} = \mathbf{R}_\phi \cdot \frac{\mathbf{y}_s}{\|\mathbf{y}_s\|} = \mathbf{R}_\phi \cdot \mathbf{y}_s \quad (25b)$$

Notice that the last equality in expression (25a) holds since $-\pi/2 < \psi \circ f_1 < \pi/2$ for all $r \in \mathbb{R}$. The normalized material basis vectors $\mathring{\mathbf{a}}_1$ and $\mathring{\mathbf{a}}_2$ may be further developed to yield

$$\begin{aligned} \mathring{\mathbf{a}}_1 &= \mathbf{R}_\phi \cdot [\cos(\psi \circ f_1)\mathbf{y}_r] \\ &= \mathbf{R}_\phi \cdot [\cos(\psi \circ f_1)\mathbf{e}_1 + \sin(\psi \circ f_1)\mathbf{e}_2] \\ &= \mathbf{R}_\phi \cdot \mathbf{R}_{\psi \circ f_1} \cdot \mathbf{e}_1 \end{aligned} \quad (26a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \mathbf{R}_{\phi + \psi \circ f_1} \cdot \mathbf{e}_1 \\ \mathring{\mathbf{a}}_2 &= \mathbf{R}_\phi \cdot \mathbf{e}_2. \end{aligned} \quad (26b)$$

Introducing the angles $\theta_1 \equiv \phi + \psi \circ f_1$ and $\theta_2 \equiv \phi$, equations (26) may be written more succinctly as

$$\mathring{\mathbf{a}}_i = \mathbf{R}_{\theta_i} \cdot \mathbf{e}_i \quad (27)$$

Note that the summation convention does not apply since i is not a dummy index.

5. Deformation Law for a Curvilinear Fiber Lamina

The flat composite lamina described in section 3 and represented in Fig. 2 is subjected to a prescribed deformation. This deformation is described mathematically by the linear mapping Φ introduced in (1), which relates the reference and deformed configurations. It is assumed that Φ is given by the product of three prescribed tensors,

$$\mathbf{x} = \Phi(\dot{\mathbf{x}}) = \mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{V} \cdot \mathbf{U} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{x}} \quad (28)$$

where \mathbf{R} , \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{U} are the rotation, simple shear and uniform stretch tensors, respectively. The resultant motion law for the continuum is representative of an in-plane rotation with simple shear and uniform extension or compression of the composite lamina, accordingly. Translation of the plate is not considered. Each individual tensor acting independently will be defined next.

Uniform Extension or Compression

The uniform stretch tensor for a state of 2D plane-strain is defined by

$$\mathbf{U} = U_{.j}^i \mathbf{e}_i \mathbf{e}^j \quad (29)$$

where the components $U_{.j}^i$ may be represented in matrix form as

$$[U] = \begin{bmatrix} k_1 & 0 \\ 0 & k_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (30)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are the extension ratios. Thus, attending to (19),

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{U} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{U} \cdot \mathbf{R}_\phi \cdot \mathbf{y} + \mathbf{U} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{x}}_0 \quad (31)$$

This particular transformation translates into a stretching of the plate in a direction parallel to the x^1 -axis or x^2 -axis if the extension ratios are set higher than unity and a compression otherwise, respectively. Fig. 4 shows the initial and deformed configuration of the plate after applying equation (31).

Figure 4: Initial and deformed configurations of the lamina after prescribed stretching. Initial boundary and reference fiber shown dashed.

Simple Shear

For the case of simple shear of a lamina in a direction parallel to x^1 -axis, the deformation is described by the shear tensor, \mathbf{V} , given by

$$\mathbf{V} = V_{.j}^i \mathbf{e}_i \mathbf{e}^j \quad (32)$$

where

$$[V] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & k_V \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (33)$$

The coefficient k_V is the shear coefficient and may be related to the shear angle, β , defined in Fig. and given by

$$k_V = \tan \beta_V \quad (34)$$

Figure 5: Initial and deformed configurations of the lamina after prescribed simple shear. Initial boundary and reference fiber shown dashed.

Rigid Body Rotation

When subjected to a rotation the lamina does not experience relative displacements between any two points of its domain. Yet, a prescribed rotation is included in the formulation to generalize the possible deformed configurations that may be obtained. The rotation tensor is defined as a proper orthogonal tensor \mathbf{R} , defined by

$$\mathbf{R} = R^i_j \mathbf{e}_i \mathbf{e}^j \tag{35}$$

The tensor \mathbf{R} applied to a vector defined in the reference configuration is equivalent to rotate that vector about a predefined axis. For the case of plane-strain, the rotation is taken in the plane in a counterclockwise direction, and thus the components of \mathbf{R} may be represented by the following 2×2 matrix,

$$[\mathbf{R}] = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \beta_R & -\sin \beta_R \\ \sin \beta_R & \cos \beta_R \end{bmatrix}, \tag{36}$$

For a constant angle β_R , the rotation matrix may also be denoted by \mathbf{R}_{β_R} . The inverse rotation tensor is defined by

$$\mathbf{R}^{-1} = \tilde{R}^i_j \mathbf{e}_i \mathbf{e}^j \tag{37}$$

where the components \tilde{R}^i_j are such that the following relations hold for $i, k = 1, 2$,

$$\tilde{R}^i_j R^j_k = R^i_j \tilde{R}^j_k = \delta^i_k, \tag{38}$$

Figure 6: Initial and deformed configurations of the lamina after prescribed counterclockwise rotation. Initial boundary and reference fiber shown dashed.

Combined Stretch, Simple Shear and Rotation

For the combined action of the previous deformation matrices results the general deformation law given by (28). First the plate is stretched, then sheared and finally rotated. The deformed configuration that could be obtained is shown in Fig. 7. Note that this corresponds to a general deformation law based on four parameters that should be specified.

Figure 7: Initial and deformed configurations of the lamina after prescribed stretching. Initial boundary and reference fiber shown dashed.

Local Basis in \mathcal{K} and $\mathring{\mathcal{K}}$

The local basis at every material point P in the actual reference configuration may be related to the local basis at P in the reference configuration. The local basis vectors in $\mathring{\mathcal{K}}$ are given by expression (6a) and since $\mathring{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{X}$, then

$$\mathring{\mathbf{x}}_i = \frac{\partial \mathring{\mathbf{x}}}{\partial \mathring{x}^i} = \mathbf{e}_i \tag{39}$$

Taking into account the motion law (28) and relation (6b),

$$\mathbf{x}_i = \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial \mathring{x}^i} = \mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{V} \cdot \mathbf{U} \cdot \frac{\partial \mathring{\mathbf{x}}}{\partial \mathring{x}^i} = \mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{V} \cdot \mathbf{U} \cdot \mathbf{e}_i \tag{40}$$

for \mathbf{R} , \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{U} constant in the \mathring{x}^i .

6. Constitutive Relations

A formulation is developed in order to expose the constitutive behaviour of a general hyperelastic material that combined with the deformation law yields the stresses on the lamina presented in the last section. Thus, a strain energy function is defined as a function of the Green-Lagrange strain tensor \mathbf{E} .

Locally, the lamina may be described by two different materials, namely the matrix and the fiber, with directions given by the normalized material basis vectors. Since mechanical properties of the materials associated with each direction are different and those directions are not orthogonal to each other then the material may be classified locally as an anisotropic material with parallelogram structure [9] and may be referred to as a clinotropic material [10, 11].

In order to account for the nonlinear behaviour of the flexible matrix a fourth order tensor function is adopted

Isotropic Material

The strain-energy function or stored-energy function is assumed to be an isotropic scalar function of a single second-order tensor \mathbf{A} ,

$$\Psi = \Psi(\mathbf{A}). \quad (41)$$

Following Itskov [12], Ψ is an isotropic function of \mathbf{A} if it satisfies the relation

$$\Psi(\mathbf{Q} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{Q}^T) = \Psi(\mathbf{A}), \quad (42)$$

for all orthogonal tensors \mathbf{Q} . If the tensor \mathbf{A} is also assumed to be symmetric, which is equivalent to the condition $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A}^T$, then Ψ becomes an isotropic tensor function of a symmetric tensor and can be expressed in terms of its eigenvalues, principal invariants or principal traces of \mathbf{A} [12, 13], which may be stated as

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi(\mathbf{A}) &= \check{\Psi}(I_{1\mathbf{A}}, I_{2\mathbf{A}}, I_{3\mathbf{A}}) \\ &= \hat{\Psi}(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3) \\ &= \tilde{\Psi}(\text{tr}\mathbf{A}, \text{tr}\mathbf{A}^2, \text{tr}\mathbf{A}^3), \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

where $I_{i\mathbf{A}}$, λ_i and $\text{tr}\mathbf{A}^i$, $i = 1, 2, 3$, are the principal invariants, eigenvalues and principal traces of \mathbf{A} , respectively. They are related by the formulas,

$$I_{1\mathbf{A}} = \text{tr}\mathbf{A} = \lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3, \quad (44a)$$

$$I_{2\mathbf{A}} = \frac{1}{2} (\text{tr}^2\mathbf{A} - \text{tr}\mathbf{A}^2) = \lambda_1\lambda_2 + \lambda_1\lambda_3 + \lambda_2\lambda_3, \quad (44b)$$

$$I_{3\mathbf{A}} = \det\mathbf{A} = \frac{1}{3} \left(\text{tr}\mathbf{A}^3 - \frac{3}{2}\text{tr}\mathbf{A}^2\text{tr}\mathbf{A} + \frac{1}{2}\text{tr}^3\mathbf{A} \right) = \lambda_1\lambda_2\lambda_3, \quad (44c)$$

The strain-energy function of an isotropic material may be defined as a function of the Green-Lagrange strain tensor \mathbf{E} , such that

$$\Psi(\mathbf{Q} \cdot \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{Q}^T) = \Psi(\mathbf{E}), \quad (45)$$

for all orthogonal tensors \mathbf{Q} . Since \mathbf{E} is symmetric, relations (43) hold and the strain-energy function may be expressed as a function of the invariants of \mathbf{E} given by $I_{1\mathbf{E}}$, $I_{2\mathbf{E}}$ and $I_{3\mathbf{E}}$. Murnaghan [14] considered the strain energy function in the form of a power series of the invariants,

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi(\mathbf{E}) &= \Psi_0 + \alpha I_{1\mathbf{E}} + \frac{\gamma + 2\mu}{2} I_{1\mathbf{E}}^2 - 2\mu I_{2\mathbf{E}} \\ &\quad + \frac{l + 2m}{3} I_{1\mathbf{E}}^3 - 2m I_{1\mathbf{E}} I_{2\mathbf{E}} + n I_{3\mathbf{E}}, \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

where the term Ψ_0 is independent of \mathbf{E} and may be determined by the requirement of vanishing stored-energy at the undeformed state. The parameters γ and μ are the Lamé coefficients and l , m and n are nonlinear coefficients, [14, 15]. The power series may be developed further up to the fourth-order [16],

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi(\mathbf{E}) &= \Psi_0 + \alpha I_{1\mathbf{E}} + \frac{\gamma + 2\mu}{2} I_{1\mathbf{E}}^2 - 2\mu I_{2\mathbf{E}} \\ &\quad + \frac{l + 2m}{3} I_{1\mathbf{E}}^3 - 2m I_{1\mathbf{E}} I_{2\mathbf{E}} + n I_{3\mathbf{E}} \\ &\quad + a_1 I_{1\mathbf{E}}^4 + a_2 I_{1\mathbf{E}}^2 I_{2\mathbf{E}} + a_3 I_{1\mathbf{E}} I_{3\mathbf{E}} + a_4 I_{2\mathbf{E}}^2, \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

If only the second order terms are considered in (47) the strain-energy function takes the form of the Saint-Venant Kirchhoff model, which is valid for hyperelastic materials. According to relations (44), the strain-energy function may be cast in terms of the principal traces of \mathbf{E} as

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi(\mathbf{E}) &= \Psi_0 + \alpha \text{tr}\mathbf{E} + \frac{\gamma}{2} \text{tr}^2\mathbf{E} + \mu \text{tr}\mathbf{E}^2 \\ &\quad + \frac{\nu_1}{3!} \text{tr}^3\mathbf{E} + \nu_2 \text{tr}\mathbf{E}^2 \text{tr}\mathbf{E} + \nu_3 \text{tr}\mathbf{E}^3 \\ &\quad + \frac{\tilde{a}_1}{4!} \text{tr}^4\mathbf{E} + \tilde{a}_2 \text{tr}\mathbf{E}^2 \text{tr}^2\mathbf{E} + \tilde{a}_3 \text{tr}\mathbf{E}^3 \text{tr}\mathbf{E} + \tilde{a}_4 \text{tr}^2\mathbf{E}^2, \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

where third-order coefficients are defined as $\nu_1 = 2l - 2m + n$, $\nu_2 = m - n/2$, $\nu_3 = n/3$, and the fourth-order coefficients are defined as $\tilde{a}_1 = 24a_1 + 12a_2 + 4a_3 + 6a_4$, $\tilde{a}_2 = -(a_2 + a_3 + a_4)/2$, $\tilde{a}_3 = a_3/3$, $\tilde{a}_4 = a_4/4$.

Transversely Isotropic Material

For an anisotropic material, relation (45) does not hold for all orthogonal tensors \mathbf{Q} . For the special case where the material can be regarded as transversely isotropic, relation (45) is still satisfied for a subgroup of all orthogonal transformations, called the transversely isotropic symmetry group, \mathcal{M}_t .

Consider the case of a fiber reinforced material with an isotropic matrix and one family of fibers. Let the set of vectors $\{\hat{\mathbf{a}}_1, \hat{\mathbf{a}}_2, \hat{\mathbf{a}}_3\}$ be an orthonormal basis such that $\hat{\mathbf{a}}_1$ define the direction of each fiber at an arbitrary point of the undeformed body, $\hat{\mathbf{a}}_3$ is normal to the midsurface of the lamina and $\hat{\mathbf{a}}_2 = \hat{\mathbf{a}}_3 \times \hat{\mathbf{a}}_1$. This set of vectors define a local Cartesian frame at each point on the midsurface of the lamina, called the local material frame. Introducing the tensor

$$\mathbf{L}_1 = \hat{\mathbf{a}}_1 \hat{\mathbf{a}}_1, \quad (49)$$

called structural tensor, the transversely isotropic symmetry group can be defined by

$$\mathcal{M}_t = \{\mathbf{Q} : \mathbf{Q}^T \cdot \mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{I} \cap \mathbf{Q} \cdot \mathbf{L}_1 \cdot \mathbf{Q}^T = \mathbf{L}_1\} \quad (50)$$

This definition represents an additional restriction on the set of all orthogonal tensors. The transversely isotropic symmetry group preserves the tensor \mathbf{L}_1 under an orthogonal transformation.

The definition of \mathbf{L}_1 can be extended by the introduction of two additional tensors with respect to the vectors $\hat{\mathbf{a}}_2$ and $\hat{\mathbf{a}}_3$,

$$\mathbf{L}_2 = \hat{\mathbf{a}}_2 \hat{\mathbf{a}}_2, \quad \mathbf{L}_3 = \hat{\mathbf{a}}_3 \hat{\mathbf{a}}_3 \quad (51)$$

Since the strain-energy for the transversely isotropic material is invariant only within the subgroup \mathcal{M} of all orthogonal transformations, it is not an isotropic function of \mathbf{E} in the sense of (42) and so is said to be anisotropic. However, the principle of isotropy of space [11] states that it is possible to express constitutive laws in unified isotropic forms regardless of the material symmetry. Following the isotropization [11] or Rychlewski's theorem [9, 12], there exists an equivalent isotropic function $\check{\Psi}$ of both \mathbf{E} and the structural tensor \mathbf{L}_1 such that,

$$\Psi(\mathbf{E}) = \check{\Psi}(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{L}_1) \quad (52)$$

Since both \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{L}_1 are symmetric tensors, then $\check{\Psi}$ may be expressed as a function of the following invariants,

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{tr}\mathbf{E}, \text{tr}\mathbf{E}^2, \text{tr}\mathbf{E}^3, \text{tr}\mathbf{L}_1, \text{tr}\mathbf{L}_1^2, \text{tr}\mathbf{L}_1^3 \\ & \text{tr}(\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{L}_1), \text{tr}(\mathbf{E}^2 \cdot \mathbf{L}_1), \text{tr}(\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{L}_1^2), \text{tr}(\mathbf{E}^2 \cdot \mathbf{L}_1^2) \end{aligned}$$

Taking into account the following identities,

$$\mathbf{L}_1^k = \mathbf{L}_1, \quad \text{tr}\mathbf{L}_1^k = 1,$$

the number of invariants can be reduced to five,

$$\text{tr}\mathbf{E}, \text{tr}\mathbf{E}^2, \text{tr}\mathbf{E}^3, \text{tr}(\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{L}_1), \text{tr}(\mathbf{E}^2 \cdot \mathbf{L}_1),$$

Thus the strain-energy function takes the form

$$\Psi(\mathbf{E}) = \check{\Psi}(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{L}_1) = \check{\Psi}\left(\text{tr}\mathbf{E}, \text{tr}\mathbf{E}^2, \text{tr}\mathbf{E}^3, \text{tr}(\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{L}_1), \text{tr}(\mathbf{E}^2 \cdot \mathbf{L}_1)\right), \quad (53)$$

The fourth order strain-energy function for an isotropic material expressed by (48) is taken as a starting point for the derivation of the strain-energy for a transversely isotropic material. Introducing the tensors $\mathbf{E}_i = \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{L}_i$, $i=1, 2, 3$, and taking into account the following identities

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{I} &= \sum_i^3 \mathbf{L}_i, \\ \mathbf{E} &= \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{I} = \mathbf{E} \cdot \sum_i^3 \mathbf{L}_i = \sum_i^3 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{L}_i = \sum_i^3 \mathbf{E}_i, \\ \mathbf{E}^m &= \underbrace{\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} \cdots \mathbf{E}}_{m \text{ times}} = \sum_{i_1}^3 \mathbf{E}_{i_1} \cdot \sum_{i_2}^3 \mathbf{E}_{i_2} \cdots \sum_{i_m}^3 \mathbf{E}_{i_m} \\ &= \sum_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_m}^3 \mathbf{E}_{i_1} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{i_2} \cdots \mathbf{E}_{i_m}, \end{aligned}$$

then, each term of the strain-energy function given by (48) that is dependent on \mathbf{E} may be expressed by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{tr} \mathbf{E}^m &= \text{tr} \left(\sum_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_m}^3 \mathbf{E}_{i_1} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{i_2} \cdots \mathbf{E}_{i_m} \right) = \sum_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_m}^3 \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_{i_1} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{i_2} \cdots \mathbf{E}_{i_m}), \\ \text{tr}^m \mathbf{E} &= \underbrace{\text{tr} \mathbf{E} \text{tr} \mathbf{E} \cdots \text{tr} \mathbf{E}}_{m \text{ times}} = \sum_{i_1}^3 \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{i_1} \sum_{i_2}^3 \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{i_2} \cdots \sum_{i_m}^3 \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{i_m} \\ &= \sum_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_m}^3 \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{i_1} \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{i_2} \cdots \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{i_m}, \end{aligned}$$

Substituting in (48) yields,

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi(\mathbf{E}) &= \Psi_0 + \alpha \sum_i^3 \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_i + \frac{\gamma}{2} \sum_{i,j}^3 \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_i \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_j + \mu \sum_{i,j}^3 \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j) \\ &+ \frac{\nu_1}{3!} \sum_{i,j,k}^3 \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_i \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_j \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_k + \nu_2 \sum_{i,j,k}^3 \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j) \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_k \\ &+ \nu_3 \sum_{i,j,k}^3 \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j \cdot \mathbf{E}_k) + \frac{\tilde{a}_1}{4!} \sum_{i,j,k,l}^3 \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_i \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_j \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_k \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_l \\ &+ \tilde{a}_2 \sum_{i,j,k,l}^3 \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j) \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_k \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_l + \tilde{a}_3 \sum_{i,j,k,l}^3 \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j \cdot \mathbf{E}_k) \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_l \\ &+ \tilde{a}_4 \sum_{i,j,k,l}^3 \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j) \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_k \cdot \mathbf{E}_l), \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

The dependence of this form of the strain-energy function upon the first four invariants can be easily verified. The fifth invariant, $\text{tr} (\mathbf{E}^2 \cdot \mathbf{L}_1)$, is also present in expression (54) through the terms $\text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j)$ since

$$\text{tr} (\mathbf{E}^2 \cdot \mathbf{L}_j) = \text{tr} (\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E}_j) = \text{tr} \left(\sum_i^3 \mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j \right) = \sum_i^3 \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j), \quad (55)$$

and so

$$\begin{aligned}\sum_{i,j}^3 \text{tr}(\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j) &= \sum_j^3 \left(\sum_i^3 \text{tr}(\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j) \right) = \sum_j^3 \text{tr}(\mathbf{E}^2 \cdot \mathbf{L}_j) \\ &= \text{tr}(\mathbf{E}^2 \cdot \mathbf{L}_1) + \text{tr}(\mathbf{E}^2 \cdot \mathbf{L}_2) + \text{tr}(\mathbf{E}^2 \cdot \mathbf{L}_3).\end{aligned}\quad (56)$$

The coefficients α , γ , μ , ν_i and \tilde{a}_i are now functions of the invariants and are defined as,

$$\alpha(\text{tr}\mathbf{E}, \text{tr}\mathbf{E}^2, \text{tr}\mathbf{E}^3, \text{tr}\mathbf{E}_1, \text{tr}(\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E}_1)) = \frac{\sum_i^3 \alpha_i \text{tr}\mathbf{E}_i}{\sum_i^3 \text{tr}\mathbf{E}_i}, \quad (57)$$

where the α_i are constant coefficients that characterize the material anisotropy. The other coefficients of equation (48) may be defined in a similar fashion. Direct substitution in (48) results in

$$\begin{aligned}\Psi(\mathbf{E}) &= \Psi_0 + \sum_i^3 \alpha_i \text{tr}\mathbf{E}_i + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j}^3 \gamma_{ij} \text{tr}\mathbf{E}_i \text{tr}\mathbf{E}_j + \sum_{i,j}^3 \mu_{ij} \text{tr}(\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j) \\ &+ \frac{1}{3!} \sum_{i,j,k}^3 \nu_{1_{ijk}} \text{tr}\mathbf{E}_i \text{tr}\mathbf{E}_j \text{tr}\mathbf{E}_k + \sum_{i,j,k}^3 \nu_{2_{ijk}} \text{tr}(\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j) \text{tr}\mathbf{E}_k \\ &+ \sum_{i,j,k}^3 \nu_{3_{ijk}} \text{tr}(\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j \cdot \mathbf{E}_k) + \frac{1}{4!} \sum_{i,j,k,l}^3 \tilde{a}_{1_{ijkl}} \text{tr}\mathbf{E}_i \text{tr}\mathbf{E}_j \text{tr}\mathbf{E}_k \text{tr}\mathbf{E}_l \\ &+ \sum_{i,j,k,l}^3 \tilde{a}_{2_{ijkl}} \text{tr}(\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j) \text{tr}\mathbf{E}_k \text{tr}\mathbf{E}_l + \sum_{i,j,k,l}^3 \tilde{a}_{3_{ijkl}} \text{tr}(\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j \cdot \mathbf{E}_k) \text{tr}\mathbf{E}_l \\ &+ \sum_{i,j,k,l}^3 \tilde{a}_{4_{ijkl}} \text{tr}(\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j) \text{tr}(\mathbf{E}_k \cdot \mathbf{E}_l).\end{aligned}\quad (58)$$

The component form of the strain-energy function given by (58) may be obtained by considering the representation of the Green-Lagrange strain tensor in the material frame. Let \bar{E}^{ij} be the contravariant components of \mathbf{E} with respect to the material frame. Then \mathbf{E} may be expressed by

$$\mathbf{E} = \bar{E}^{ij} \hat{\mathbf{a}}_i \hat{\mathbf{a}}_j. \quad (59)$$

Since in this case the material frame vectors form an orthonormal basis, then $\hat{\mathbf{a}}_i \cdot \hat{\mathbf{a}}_j = \delta_j^i$ and $\bar{E}^{ij} = \bar{E}_{ij}$, $\hat{\mathbf{a}}_i = \hat{\mathbf{a}}^i$, thus equation (59) may be rewritten as

$$\mathbf{E} = \bar{E}_{ij} \hat{\mathbf{a}}_i \hat{\mathbf{a}}_j. \quad (60)$$

Taking into account the following relations

$$\begin{aligned}\text{tr}\mathbf{E}_i &= \mathbf{E}^T : \mathbf{L}_i = \bar{E}_{ii}, \\ \text{tr}(\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j) &= \mathbf{E}^T : \mathbf{L}_i \cdot \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{L}_j = \bar{E}_{ij} \bar{E}_{ji} = \bar{E}_{ij}^2, \\ \text{tr}(\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j \cdot \mathbf{E}_k) &= \mathbf{E}^T : \mathbf{L}_i \cdot \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{L}_j \cdot \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{L}_k = \bar{E}_{ij} \bar{E}_{jk} \bar{E}_{ki},\end{aligned}$$

then the terms in equation (58) may be expressed in component form by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Psi(\bar{E}_{pq}) = & \Psi_0 + \sum_i^3 \alpha_i \bar{E}_{ii} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j}^3 \gamma_{ij} \bar{E}_{ii} \bar{E}_{jj} + \sum_{i,j}^3 \mu_{ij} \bar{E}_{ij}^2 \\
 & + \frac{1}{3!} \sum_{i,j,k}^3 \nu_{1_{ijk}} \bar{E}_{ii} \bar{E}_{jj} \bar{E}_{kk} + \sum_{i,j,k}^3 \nu_{2_{ijk}} \bar{E}_{ij}^2 \bar{E}_{kk} + \sum_{i,j,k}^3 \nu_{3_{ijk}} \bar{E}_{ij} \bar{E}_{jk} \bar{E}_{ki} \\
 & + \frac{1}{4!} \sum_{i,j,k,l}^3 \tilde{a}_{1_{ijkl}} \bar{E}_{ii} \bar{E}_{jj} \bar{E}_{kk} \bar{E}_{ll} + \sum_{i,j,k,l}^3 \tilde{a}_{2_{ijkl}} \bar{E}_{ij}^2 \bar{E}_{kk} \bar{E}_{ll} \\
 & + \sum_{i,j,k,l}^3 \tilde{a}_{3_{ijkl}} \bar{E}_{ij} \bar{E}_{jk} \bar{E}_{ki} \bar{E}_{ll} + \sum_{i,j,k,l}^3 \tilde{a}_{4_{ijkl}} \bar{E}_{ij}^2 \bar{E}_{kl}^2,
 \end{aligned} \tag{61}$$

where for convenience $\Psi(\bar{E}_{pq}) = \Psi(\bar{E}_{11}, \bar{E}_{12}, \bar{E}_{13}, \bar{E}_{22}, \bar{E}_{23}, \bar{E}_{33})$.

The general form for the strain-energy function in terms of components of the Green-Lagrange strain tensor, as given by (61), does not satisfy the requirement of existence of natural state. This requirement implies that the strain-energy function and stresses identically vanish in the undeformed or reference configuration. Since in the reference configuration $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{I}$, then $\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{0}$. Hence the natural state requirement can be satisfied by the following conditions

$$\Psi(\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{0}) = 0 \tag{62}$$

$$\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{0}) = \left. \frac{d\Psi}{d\mathbf{E}} \right|_{\mathbf{E}=\mathbf{0}} = 0 \tag{63}$$

It can be verified that these conditions are satisfied by the strain-energy function given by (58) if $\Psi_0 = 0$ and $\alpha_i = 0$.

The strain-energy function can be further simplified considering the plate to be in a state of plane-strain, where $\bar{E}_{33} = \bar{E}_{13} = \bar{E}_{31} = \bar{E}_{23} = \bar{E}_{32} = 0$.

Taking these assumptions into account and after expanding (61) and collecting powers of \bar{E}_{11} , \bar{E}_{22} and \bar{E}_{12} the strain-energy function results in

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Psi(\bar{E}_{pq}) = & \frac{1}{2} c_{11} \bar{E}_{11}^2 + c_{12} \bar{E}_{11} \bar{E}_{22} + \frac{1}{2} c_{22} \bar{E}_{22}^2 + 2c_{66} \bar{E}_{12}^2 \\
 & + \frac{1}{3} c_{111} \bar{E}_{11}^3 + c_{112} \bar{E}_{11}^2 \bar{E}_{22} + c_{122} \bar{E}_{11} \bar{E}_{22}^2 + \frac{1}{3} c_{222} \bar{E}_{22}^3 \\
 & + 2c_{661} \bar{E}_{12}^2 \bar{E}_{11} + 2c_{662} \bar{E}_{12}^2 \bar{E}_{22} + \frac{1}{4} c_{1111} \bar{E}_{11}^4 + c_{1112} \bar{E}_{11}^3 \bar{E}_{22} \\
 & + \frac{3}{2} c_{1122} \bar{E}_{11}^2 \bar{E}_{22}^2 + c_{1222} \bar{E}_{11} \bar{E}_{22}^3 + \frac{1}{4} c_{2222} \bar{E}_{22}^4 \\
 & + 2c_{6611} \bar{E}_{12}^2 \bar{E}_{11}^2 + 4c_{6612} \bar{E}_{12}^2 \bar{E}_{11} \bar{E}_{22} + 2c_{6622} \bar{E}_{12}^2 \bar{E}_{22}^2 \\
 & + 4c_{6666} \bar{E}_{12}^4,
 \end{aligned} \tag{64}$$

where the relation between the newly defined constants and the coefficients of (61) for plane-strain are given in appendix A. Notice that terms involving odd powers of \bar{E}_{12} do not appear in expression (64).

The strain-energy function may be stated in tensor form by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Psi(\mathbf{E}) = & \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j}^2 c_{ij} \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_i \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_j + c_{66} \sum_{i,j \neq i}^2 \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j) + \frac{1}{3} \sum_{i,j,k}^2 c_{ijk} \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_i \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_j \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_k \\
 & + \sum_{i,j \neq i,k}^2 c_{66k} \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j \cdot \mathbf{E}_k) + \frac{1}{4} \sum_{i,j,k,l}^2 c_{ijkl} \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_i \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_j \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_k \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_l \\
 & + \sum_{i,j \neq i,k,l}^2 c_{66kl} \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j) \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_k \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_l + 2c_{6666} \sum_{i,j \neq i}^2 \text{tr}^2 (\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j),
 \end{aligned} \tag{65}$$

where, for $i, j = 1, 2$ and $i \neq j$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 c_{ij} &= c_{ji}, \\
 c_{ijj} &= c_{iji} = c_{jii}, \\
 c_{ijij} &= c_{ijji} = c_{jijj} = c_{jiii}, \\
 c_{ijjj} &= c_{jjii} = c_{ijji} = c_{jijj} = c_{ijij} = c_{jiji}, \\
 c_{66ij} &= c_{66ji}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{66}$$

First and Second Piola-Kirchhoff Stress Tensors

The second Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor, \mathbf{S} , may be obtained from the derivative of the strain-energy function given by (65),

$$\mathbf{S} = \frac{d\Psi(\mathbf{E})}{d\mathbf{E}}. \tag{67}$$

Notice that the strain-energy function is a scalar valued function of a symmetric tensor. Thus it is defined only in a subset of all second order tensors defined by

$$\mathcal{S}_{ym}^2 = \{\mathbf{A} : \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A}^T\} \tag{68}$$

Following the convention by Itskov [12] regarding the derivative of symmetric tensor functions, it is assumed that the derivative given by (67) belongs to the same subset of its argument \mathbf{E} , which implies that

$$\frac{d\Psi(\mathbf{E})}{d\mathbf{E}} \in \mathcal{S}_{ym}^2 \quad \text{for } \mathbf{E} \in \mathcal{S}_{ym}^2. \tag{69}$$

The derivative given by (67) is then calculated as follows,

$$\frac{d\Psi(\mathbf{E})}{d\mathbf{E}} = \frac{d\Psi(\mathbf{A})}{d \text{sym} \mathbf{A}} = \text{sym} \left[\frac{d\Psi(\mathbf{A})}{d\mathbf{A}} \right], \tag{70}$$

where the tensor \mathbf{A} is obtained by notionally extending the definition of \mathbf{E} such that it is no longer assumed to be symmetric and

$$\text{sym} \mathbf{A} = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{A}^T). \tag{71}$$

Attending to the relations (66) and to appendix B, the derivative of the strain-energy function may

be expressed by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{S} = & \sum_{i,j}^2 c_{ij} (\text{tr} \mathbf{E}_i) \mathbf{L}_j + 2c_{66} \sum_{i,j \neq i}^2 \mathbf{L}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j + \sum_{i,j,k}^2 c_{ijk} (\text{tr} \mathbf{E}_i \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_j) \mathbf{L}_k \\
 & + 2 \sum_{i,j \neq i}^2 c_{66i} [\mathbf{L}_i \cdot (\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j + \mathbf{E}_j \cdot \mathbf{E}_i) + \mathbf{L}_j \cdot \mathbf{E}_i^2] \\
 & + \sum_{i,j,k,l}^2 c_{ijkl} (\text{tr} \mathbf{E}_i \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_j \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_k) \mathbf{L}_l \\
 & + 2 \sum_{i,j \neq i,k,l}^2 c_{66kl} \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_k [(\text{tr} \mathbf{E}_l) \mathbf{L}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j + \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j) \mathbf{L}_l] \\
 & + 8c_{6666} \sum_{i,j \neq i}^2 \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j) \mathbf{L}_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_j.
 \end{aligned} \tag{72}$$

The second Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor can be resolved for the material tensor basis,

$$\mathbf{S} = \bar{S}^{ij} \hat{\mathbf{a}}_i \hat{\mathbf{a}}_j. \tag{73}$$

Since the material frame is locally a Cartesian frame, then $\bar{S}^{ij} = \bar{S}_{ij}$ and

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{S}_{11} = & c_{11} \bar{E}_{11} + c_{12} \bar{E}_{22} + 2c_{661} \bar{E}_{12}^2 + c_{111} \bar{E}_{11}^2 + 2c_{112} \bar{E}_{11} \bar{E}_{22} \\
 & + c_{122} \bar{E}_{22}^2 + 4c_{6611} \bar{E}_{12}^2 \bar{E}_{11} + 4c_{6612} \bar{E}_{12}^2 \bar{E}_{22} + c_{1111} \bar{E}_{11}^3 \\
 & + 3c_{1112} \bar{E}_{11}^2 \bar{E}_{22} + 3c_{1122} \bar{E}_{11} \bar{E}_{22}^2 + c_{1222} \bar{E}_{22}^3,
 \end{aligned} \tag{74}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{S}_{12} = \bar{S}_{21} = & 2c_{66} \bar{E}_{12} + 2c_{661} \bar{E}_{12} \bar{E}_{11} + 2c_{662} \bar{E}_{12} \bar{E}_{22} \\
 & + 2c_{6611} \bar{E}_{12} \bar{E}_{11}^2 + 4c_{6612} \bar{E}_{12} \bar{E}_{11} \bar{E}_{22} + 2c_{6622} \bar{E}_{12} \bar{E}_{22}^2 \\
 & + 8c_{6666} \bar{E}_{12}^3,
 \end{aligned} \tag{75}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{S}_{22} = & c_{22} \bar{E}_{22} + c_{12} \bar{E}_{11} + 2c_{662} \bar{E}_{12}^2 + c_{112} \bar{E}_{11}^2 + 2c_{122} \bar{E}_{11} \bar{E}_{22} \\
 & + c_{222} \bar{E}_{22}^2 + 4c_{6612} \bar{E}_{12}^2 \bar{E}_{11} + 4c_{6622} \bar{E}_{12}^2 \bar{E}_{22} + c_{1112} \bar{E}_{11}^3 \\
 & + 3c_{1122} \bar{E}_{11}^2 \bar{E}_{22} + 3c_{1222} \bar{E}_{11} \bar{E}_{22}^2 + c_{2222} \bar{E}_{22}^3,
 \end{aligned} \tag{76}$$

The first and second Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensors are related by

$$\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{F}^T. \tag{77}$$

The deformation gradient, \mathbf{F} , follows from definition (5) and attending that

$$\mathbf{x}_j = \hat{F}_{,j}^i \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i \tag{78}$$

it may be expressed with respect to the initial local basis by

$$\mathbf{F} = \hat{F}_{,j}^i \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i \hat{\mathbf{x}}^j, \tag{79}$$

and the basis $\{\hat{\mathbf{x}}_1, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_2\}$ is related to the material basis $\hat{\mathbf{a}}_1, \hat{\mathbf{a}}_2$ at each point through orthogonal transformations represented by the rotation tensors \mathbf{R}_{θ_1} and \mathbf{R}_{θ_2} , respectively, as given by equations (27).

Let the contravariant components of \mathbf{P} with respect to the global frame be defined by P^{ij} . Then \mathbf{P} may be expressed by

$$\mathbf{P} = \mathring{P}^{ij} \mathring{\mathbf{x}}_i \mathring{\mathbf{x}}_j. \quad (80)$$

Substituting expressions (73) and (79) in (77) results in

$$\mathbf{P} = \bar{S}^{ij} \mathring{\mathbf{a}}_i \mathring{\mathbf{a}}_j \cdot \left(\mathring{F}_{.m}^k \mathring{\mathbf{x}}_k \mathring{\mathbf{x}}^m \right)^T = \bar{S}^{ij} \mathring{F}_{.m}^k (\mathring{\mathbf{a}}_j \cdot \mathring{\mathbf{x}}^m) \mathring{\mathbf{a}}_i \mathring{\mathbf{x}}_k, \quad (81)$$

but from (27),

$$\mathring{\mathbf{a}}_i \cdot \mathring{\mathbf{x}}^j = \mathring{\mathbf{x}}^j \cdot \mathring{\mathbf{a}}_i = \mathring{\mathbf{x}}^j \cdot \mathbf{R}_{\theta_i} \cdot \mathring{\mathbf{x}}_i = (R_i^j)_{\theta_i}$$

and

$$\mathring{\mathbf{a}}_i = (R_i^j)_{\theta_i} \mathring{\mathbf{x}}_j,$$

and after substituting back in expression (81) and rearranging terms yields

$$\mathbf{P} = (R_{\underline{i}}^n)_{\theta_i} \bar{S}^{ij} (R_{\underline{j}}^m)_{\theta_j} \mathring{F}_{.m}^k \mathring{\mathbf{x}}_n \mathring{\mathbf{x}}_k, \quad (82)$$

Comparing (82) with (80) the components of \mathbf{P} with respect to the undeformed local basis are readily obtained

$$\mathring{P}^{ij} = (R_{\underline{k}}^i)_{\theta_k} \bar{S}^{km} (R_{\underline{m}}^n)_{\theta_m} \mathring{F}_{.n}^j. \quad (83)$$

Then, substituting for the components of \mathbf{R}_{θ_i} given by equation (36), equation (83) can be written in the following explicit form

$$\begin{aligned} \mathring{P}^{11} &= \left(\mathring{F}_{.1}^1 \cos^2 \theta_1 + \mathring{F}_{.2}^1 \cos \theta_1 \sin \theta_1 \right) \bar{S}_{11} \\ &+ \left(\mathring{F}_{.1}^1 \sin^2 \theta_2 - \mathring{F}_{.2}^1 \cos \theta_2 \sin \theta_2 \right) \bar{S}_{22} \\ &+ \left[-2\mathring{F}_{.1}^1 \cos \theta_1 \sin \theta_2 + \mathring{F}_{.2}^1 (\cos \theta_1 \cos \theta_2 - \sin \theta_1 \sin \theta_2) \right] \bar{S}_{12}, \end{aligned} \quad (84)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathring{P}^{22} &= \left(\mathring{F}_{.2}^2 \sin^2 \theta_1 + \mathring{F}_{.1}^2 \cos \theta_1 \sin \theta_1 \right) \bar{S}_{11} \\ &+ \left(\mathring{F}_{.2}^2 \cos^2 \theta_2 - \mathring{F}_{.1}^2 \cos \theta_2 \sin \theta_2 \right) \bar{S}_{22} \\ &+ \left[2\mathring{F}_{.2}^2 \cos \theta_2 \sin \theta_1 + \mathring{F}_{.1}^2 (\cos \theta_1 \cos \theta_2 - \sin \theta_1 \sin \theta_2) \right] \bar{S}_{12}, \end{aligned} \quad (85)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathring{P}^{12} &= \left(\mathring{F}_{.1}^2 \cos^2 \theta_1 + \mathring{F}_{.2}^2 \cos \theta_1 \sin \theta_1 \right) \bar{S}_{11} \\ &+ \left(\mathring{F}_{.1}^2 \sin^2 \theta_2 - \mathring{F}_{.2}^2 \cos \theta_2 \sin \theta_2 \right) \bar{S}_{22} \\ &+ \left[-2\mathring{F}_{.1}^2 \cos \theta_1 \sin \theta_2 + \mathring{F}_{.2}^2 (\cos \theta_1 \cos \theta_2 - \sin \theta_1 \sin \theta_2) \right] \bar{S}_{12}, \end{aligned} \quad (86)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathring{P}^{21} &= \left(\mathring{F}_{.2}^1 \sin^2 \theta_1 + \mathring{F}_{.1}^1 \cos \theta_1 \sin \theta_1 \right) \bar{S}_{11} \\ &+ \left(\mathring{F}_{.2}^1 \cos^2 \theta_2 - \mathring{F}_{.1}^1 \cos \theta_2 \sin \theta_2 \right) \bar{S}_{22} \\ &+ \left[2\mathring{F}_{.2}^1 \cos \theta_2 \sin \theta_1 + \mathring{F}_{.1}^1 (\cos \theta_1 \cos \theta_2 - \sin \theta_1 \sin \theta_2) \right] \bar{S}_{12}. \end{aligned} \quad (87)$$

Clinotropic Material

A clinotropic material is characterized by two non-orthogonal and mechanically non-equivalent directions [10]. Monoclinic crystals and composite materials reinforced with two families of fibers where each family has distinct material properties and is laid in a non-orthogonal direction to the other are examples of clinotropic materials. Clinotropic reinforced composite materials are said to have a parallelogram structure [9].

Consider the case of the curvilinear fiber reinforced material described in section 3 and represented in Fig. 2. The normalized material basis vectors were introduced in section 4 and are given by expressions (27). Since this set of vectors define two non-orthogonal directions associated to different material properties at each point, then locally this material is characterized by clinotropic symmetry.

The form of the strain-energy function as given by (45) is now only valid for a restricted group of orthogonal second-order tensors. This group may be obtained from the full symmetry group defined in [9],

$$\mathcal{H} = \{ \mathbf{Q} : \mathbf{Q}^T \cdot \mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{I} \cap \mathbf{Q} \cdot \mathbf{L}_i \cdot \mathbf{Q}^T = \mathbf{L}_{\sigma(i)}, i = 1, \dots, N, \text{ for some } \sigma \in S_{\{1, \dots, N\}} \} \quad (88)$$

where σ and $S_{\{1, \dots, N\}}$ are the permutation map and the full symmetric group on the set $\{1, \dots, N\}$, respectively.

A material with clinotropic symmetry may be described by three crystallographic point groups, \mathcal{M}_{c_1} , \mathcal{M}_{c_2} and \mathcal{M}_{c_3} , that consist in combinations of positive and negative second-order identity and reflection tensors [10]. Only \mathcal{M}_{c_3} corresponds to the parallelogram structure of a fiber reinforced composite and is obtained for the identity permutation, $\sigma(i) = i$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$. For $N = 3$, this symmetry group is defined by

$$\mathcal{M}_{c_3} = \{ \mathbf{Q} : \mathbf{Q}^T \cdot \mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{I} \cap \mathbf{Q} \cdot \mathbf{L}_i \cdot \mathbf{Q}^T = \mathbf{L}_i, i = 1, 2, 3 \} \quad (89)$$

and the only second-order tensors satisfying conditions in (89) are the identity tensor \mathbf{I} and reflection tensor \mathbf{N} in the fiber plane. Hence,

$$\mathcal{M}_{c_3} = \{ \mathbf{I}, -\mathbf{I}, \mathbf{N}, -\mathbf{N} \} \quad (90)$$

and for $N = 2$, the symmetry group reduces to

$$\mathcal{M}_{c_3} = \{ \mathbf{I}, -\mathbf{I} \}. \quad (91)$$

According to Rychlewski's theorem, there exists an isotropic function $\check{\Psi}(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{L}_1, \mathbf{L}_2)$ such that

$$\Psi(\mathbf{E}) = \check{\Psi}(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{L}_1, \mathbf{L}_2) \quad (92)$$

The strain-energy function is now dependent on 9 invariants [10], and may be cast in the form

$$\Psi(\mathbf{E}) = \check{\Psi} \left(\text{tr} \mathbf{E}, \text{tr} \mathbf{E}^2, \text{tr} \mathbf{E}^3, \text{tr} (\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{L}_1), \text{tr} (\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{L}_2), \right. \quad (93)$$

$$\left. \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}^2 \cdot \mathbf{L}_1), \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}^2 \cdot \mathbf{L}_2), \text{tr} (\mathbf{L}_1 \cdot \mathbf{L}_2), \text{tr} (\mathbf{L}_1 \cdot \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{L}_2) \right), \quad (94)$$

Again, the strain-energy function is derived from the isotropic function (48). First, and following [17, 18], we redefine the structural tensors as

$$\mathbf{L}_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} (\hat{\mathbf{a}}_i \hat{\mathbf{a}}_j + \hat{\mathbf{a}}_j \hat{\mathbf{a}}_i), \quad \text{for } i, j = 1, 2, 3 \quad (95)$$

With this redefinition, tensors \mathbf{L}_i became \mathbf{L}_{ii} , for $i = 1, 2, 3$ and for $i \neq j = 1, 2, 3$ three additional tensors are formed, such that $\mathbf{L}_{ij} = \mathbf{L}_{ji}$.

Introducing the metric tensor of the undeformed material coordinate system with components

$$\hat{g}_{ij} = \hat{\mathbf{a}}_i \cdot \hat{\mathbf{a}}_j \quad (96)$$

Note that $\overset{\circ}{g}_{ij} = 1$ for $i = j$, and taking into account relations (27),

$$\begin{aligned}
 \overset{\circ}{g}_{12} &= \overset{\circ}{g}_{21} = \hat{\mathbf{a}}_i \cdot \hat{\mathbf{a}}_j \\
 &= (\mathbf{R}_{\theta_1} \cdot \mathbf{e}_1) \cdot (\mathbf{R}_{\theta_2} \cdot \mathbf{e}_2) \\
 &= (\mathbf{e}_1 \cdot \mathbf{R}_{\theta_1}^T) \cdot (\mathbf{R}_{\theta_2} \cdot \mathbf{e}_2) \\
 &= \mathbf{e}_1 \cdot (\mathbf{R}_{\psi \circ f_1}^T \mathbf{R}_{\phi}^T) \cdot \mathbf{R}_{\phi} \cdot \mathbf{e}_2 \\
 &= \mathbf{e}_2 \cdot \mathbf{R}_{\psi \circ f_1} \cdot \mathbf{e}_1 \\
 &= (R_{21})_{\psi \circ f_1} \\
 &= \sin(\psi \circ f_1) \\
 &= \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \psi \circ f_1\right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{97}$$

where $\pi/2 - \psi \circ f_1$ is the local angle between vectors $\hat{\mathbf{a}}_1$ and $\hat{\mathbf{a}}_2$.

The unit tensor may be written with components on the material basis coordinate system in the reference configuration,

$$\mathbf{I} = \sum_{i,j} \overset{\circ}{g}^{ij} \hat{\mathbf{a}}_i \hat{\mathbf{a}}_j = \sum_{i,j} \overset{\circ}{g}^{ij} \mathbf{L}_{ij} \tag{98}$$

and the Green-Lagrange strain tensor becomes

$$\mathbf{E} = \sum_{i,j} \overset{\circ}{g}^{ij} \mathbf{E}_{ij} \tag{99}$$

where we define $\mathbf{E}_{ij} = \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{L}_{ij}$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$.

Powers of \mathbf{E} may as well be derived,

$$\mathbf{E}^m = \sum_{\substack{i_1, \dots, i_m \\ j_1, \dots, j_m}} g^{i_1 j_1} \dots g^{i_m j_m} \mathbf{E}_{i_1 j_1} \dots \mathbf{E}_{i_m j_m} \tag{100}$$

and the trace of powers of \mathbf{E} as well as powers of the traces of \mathbf{E} are given respectively by

$$\text{tr} \mathbf{E}^m = \sum_{\substack{i_1, \dots, i_m \\ j_1, \dots, j_m}} g^{i_1 j_1} \dots g^{i_m j_m} \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_{i_1 j_1} \dots \mathbf{E}_{i_m j_m}) \tag{101}$$

and

$$\text{tr}^m \mathbf{E} = \sum_{\substack{i_1, \dots, i_m \\ j_1, \dots, j_m}} g^{i_1 j_1} \dots g^{i_m j_m} \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{i_1 j_1} \dots \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{i_m j_m} \tag{102}$$

Substituting where appropriate in equation (48) yields,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Psi(\mathbf{E}) = & \Psi_0 + \sum_{i,j}^3 \alpha_{ij} g^{ij} \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{ij} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j,k,l}^3 \gamma_{ijkl} g^{ij} g^{kl} \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{ij} \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{kl} + \sum_{i,j,k,l}^3 \mu_{ijkl} g^{ij} g^{kl} \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{kl}) \\
 & + \frac{1}{3!} \sum_{i,j,k,l,m,n}^3 \nu_{ijklmn} g^{ij} g^{kl} g^{mn} \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{ij} \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{kl} \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{mn} \\
 & + \sum_{i,j,k,l,m,n}^3 \nu_{2ijklmn} g^{ij} g^{kl} g^{mn} \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{kl}) \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{mn} \\
 & + \sum_{i,j,k,l,m,n}^3 \nu_{3ijklmn} g^{ij} g^{kl} g^{mn} \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{kl} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{mn}) \\
 & + \frac{1}{4!} \sum_{\substack{i,j,k,l \\ m,n,p,q}}^3 \tilde{a}_{1ijklmnpq} g^{ij} g^{kl} g^{mn} g^{pq} \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{ij} \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{kl} \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{mn} \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{pq} \\
 & + \sum_{\substack{i,j,k,l \\ m,n,p,q}}^3 \tilde{a}_{2ijklmnpq} g^{ij} g^{kl} g^{mn} g^{pq} \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{kl}) \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{mn} \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{pq} \\
 & + \sum_{\substack{i,j,k,l \\ m,n,p,q}}^3 \tilde{a}_{3ijklmnpq} g^{ij} g^{kl} g^{mn} g^{pq} \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{kl} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{mn}) \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{pq} \\
 & + \sum_{\substack{i,j,k,l \\ m,n,p,q}}^3 \tilde{a}_{4ijklmnpq} g^{ij} g^{kl} g^{mn} g^{pq} \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{kl}) \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_{mn} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{pq}) \\
 & + \sum_{i,j \neq i}^3 \tilde{a}_{5ij} \text{tr} (\mathbf{L}_{ii} \cdot \mathbf{L}_{jj}) + \sum_{i,j \neq i, k, l \neq k}^3 \tilde{a}_{6ijkl} \text{tr} (\mathbf{L}_{ii} \cdot \mathbf{L}_{jj}) \text{tr} (\mathbf{L}_{kk} \cdot \mathbf{L}_{ll}) \\
 & + \sum_{i,j \neq i}^3 \tilde{a}_{7ij} \text{tr} (\mathbf{L}_{ii} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{jj}) + \sum_{i,j \neq i, k, l \neq k}^3 \tilde{a}_{8ijkl} \text{tr} (\mathbf{L}_{ii} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{jj}) \text{tr} (\mathbf{L}_{kk} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{ll})
 \end{aligned} \tag{103}$$

where the last four sums were added to account for the invariants $\text{tr} (\mathbf{L}_{ii} \cdot \mathbf{L}_{jj})$ and $\text{tr} (\mathbf{L}_{ii} \cdot \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{L}_{jj})$, for $i = 1, 2, 3$ and $i \neq j$.

Equation (103) may be written in terms of components of the strain tensor with respect to the material basis, if the following relations are considered,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{ij} &= \mathbf{E}^T : \mathbf{L}_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} (\bar{E}_{ij} + \bar{E}_{ji}) = \bar{E}_{ij}, \\
 \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{kl}) &= \mathbf{E}^T : \mathbf{L}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{L}_{kl} = \frac{1}{2} (\bar{E}_{ik} \bar{E}_{jl} + \bar{E}_{il} \bar{E}_{jk}), \\
 \text{tr} (\mathbf{E}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{kl} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{mn}) &= \mathbf{E}^T : \mathbf{L}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{L}_{kl} \cdot \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{L}_{mn} \\
 &= \frac{1}{8} [\bar{E}_{ik} (\bar{E}_{jm} \bar{E}_{ln} + \bar{E}_{jn} \bar{E}_{lm}) + \bar{E}_{il} (\bar{E}_{jm} \bar{E}_{kn} + \bar{E}_{jn} \bar{E}_{km}) \\
 &\quad + \bar{E}_{jk} (\bar{E}_{im} \bar{E}_{ln} + \bar{E}_{in} \bar{E}_{lm}) + \bar{E}_{jl} (\bar{E}_{im} \bar{E}_{kn} + \bar{E}_{in} \bar{E}_{km})], \\
 \text{tr} (\mathbf{L}_{ii} \cdot \mathbf{L}_{jj}) &= g_{ij}^2, \quad \text{for } i \neq j \\
 \text{tr} (\mathbf{L}_{ii} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{jj}) &= g_{ij} \bar{E}_{ij}, \quad \text{for } i \neq j.
 \end{aligned}$$

which, after substitution in (103) yields,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Psi(\mathbf{E}) = & \Psi_0 + \sum_{i,j}^3 \alpha_{ij} g^{ij} \bar{E}_{ij} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j,k,l}^3 \gamma_{ijkl} g^{ij} g^{kl} \bar{E}_{ij} \bar{E}_{kl} + \sum_{i,j,k,l}^3 \mu_{ijkl} g^{ij} g^{kl} \bar{E}_{jk} \bar{E}_{li} \\
 & + \frac{1}{3!} \sum_{i,j,k,l,m,n}^3 \nu_{1ijklmn} g^{ij} g^{kl} g^{mn} \bar{E}_{ij} \bar{E}_{kl} \bar{E}_{mn} \\
 & + \sum_{i,j,k,l,m,n}^3 \nu_{2ijklmn} g^{ij} g^{kl} g^{mn} \bar{E}_{jk} \bar{E}_{li} \bar{E}_{mn} \\
 & + \sum_{i,j,k,l,m,n}^3 \nu_{3ijklmn} g^{ij} g^{kl} g^{mn} \bar{E}_{jk} \bar{E}_{lm} \bar{E}_{ni} \\
 & + \frac{1}{4!} \sum_{\substack{i,j,k,l \\ m,n,p,q}}^3 \tilde{a}_{1ijklmnpq} g^{ij} g^{kl} g^{mn} g^{pq} \bar{E}_{ij} \bar{E}_{kl} \bar{E}_{mn} \bar{E}_{pq} \\
 & + \sum_{\substack{i,j,k,l \\ m,n,p,q}}^3 \tilde{a}_{2ijklmnpq} g^{ij} g^{kl} g^{mn} g^{pq} \bar{E}_{jk} \bar{E}_{li} \bar{E}_{mn} \bar{E}_{pq} \\
 & + \sum_{\substack{i,j,k,l \\ m,n,p,q}}^3 \tilde{a}_{3ijklmnpq} g^{ij} g^{kl} g^{mn} g^{pq} \bar{E}_{jk} \bar{E}_{lm} \bar{E}_{ni} \bar{E}_{pq} \\
 & + \sum_{\substack{i,j,k,l \\ m,n,p,q}}^3 \tilde{a}_{4ijklmnpq} g^{ij} g^{kl} g^{mn} g^{pq} \bar{E}_{jk} \bar{E}_{li} \bar{E}_{np} \bar{E}_{qm} \\
 & + \sum_{i,j \neq i}^3 \tilde{a}_{5ij} g_{ij}^2 + \sum_{i,j \neq i, k, l \neq k}^3 \tilde{a}_{6ijkl} g_{ij}^2 g_{kl}^2 \\
 & + \sum_{i,j \neq i}^3 \tilde{a}_{7ij} g_{ij} \bar{E}_{ij} + \sum_{i,j \neq i, k, l \neq k}^3 \tilde{a}_{8ijkl} g_{ij} g_{kl} \bar{E}_{ij} \bar{E}_{kl}
 \end{aligned} \tag{104}$$

In light of conditions (62), the term Ψ_0 and constants α_{ij} vanish. For a clinotropic material, however, all the remaining terms of the complete polynomial in the components of \mathbf{E} appear in formula (104). For instance, the second order terms may be given by

$$\frac{1}{2} c_{11} \bar{E}_{11}^2 + 2c_{66} \bar{E}_{12}^2 + \frac{1}{2} c_{22} \bar{E}_{22}^2 + 2c_{16} \bar{E}_{11} \bar{E}_{12} + c_{12} \bar{E}_{11} \bar{E}_{22} + 2c_{26} \bar{E}_{22} \bar{E}_{12} \tag{105}$$

7. Composite Laminate

The constitutive equations developed in the previous sections are used here to assemble the equations for a composite laminate composed of n laminae.

The overall in-plane Lagrangean stresses acting at the boundary of the laminate may be obtained by integrating the components of the Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor acting on each laminae, thus

$$N^{ij} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} P^{ij} dx^3 = \sum_{k=1}^n t P^{ij} \tag{106}$$

where h is the total thickness of the laminate, the N^{ij} are the force per unit width relative to the undeformed configuration, t is the thickness of each lamina and P^{ij} are the components of the Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor with respect to the k^{th} lamina. It is assumed that there is no interlaminar shear

deformation upon an in-plane deformation given by the deformation law (28). As such, each lamina undergoes the same deformation and there is no slip between each pair of adjacent layers.

8. Concluding Remarks

A fourth order polynomial form for the strain-energy function was proposed for three different classes of material. First the isotropic material model was developed which served as the basis for the models for transversely orthotropic and clinotropic materials. Only a clinotropic material with the parallelogram structure would account for two local material directions that are not orthogonal and have different mechanical material properties. The strain-energy function thus obtained will have all the mixed terms of the Green-Lagrange strain tensor from order two and higher. The constants appearing on this functions may be obtained from experimental fitting or from micromechanical models. Depending on the particular material, some of the constants represent interaction terms between axial and shearing strains and may be neglected [19].

Some limitations and defects inherent to the manufacturing of VSP composites, such as tow drops and overlaps are not currently addressed by the constitutive model proposed in this paper. Also fiber debonding may be relevant in flexible matrix composites, specially in the case of composite laminates reinforced with stiff fibers with low or zero curvature.

9. Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the support by the Composite Research Network (CRN), Canada.

Appendices

A. Relation between Strain-Energy coefficients

The strain-energy functions given by (61) and (64) coincide if the following relations between coefficients hold.

Second-order Coefficients

$$\begin{aligned}c_{11} &= \gamma_{11} + 2\mu_{11}, \\c_{22} &= \gamma_{22} + 2\mu_{22}, \\c_{12} &= \frac{1}{2}(\gamma_{12} + \gamma_{21}), \\c_{66} &= \frac{1}{2}(\mu_{12} + \mu_{21}).\end{aligned}$$

Third-order Coefficients

$$\begin{aligned}c_{111} &= \frac{1}{2}\nu_{1111} + 3(\nu_{2111} + \nu_{3111}), \\c_{222} &= \frac{1}{2}\nu_{1222} + 3(\nu_{2222} + \nu_{3222}), \\c_{112} &= \frac{1}{6}(\nu_{1112} + \nu_{1121} + \nu_{1211}) + \nu_{2112}, \\c_{122} &= \frac{1}{6}(\nu_{1122} + \nu_{1212} + \nu_{1221}) + \nu_{2221}, \\c_{661} &= \frac{1}{2}(\nu_{2121} + \nu_{2211} + \nu_{3112} + \nu_{3121} + \nu_{3211}), \\c_{662} &= \frac{1}{2}(\nu_{2122} + \nu_{2212} + \nu_{3122} + \nu_{3212} + \nu_{3221}).\end{aligned}$$

Fourth-order Coefficients

$$\begin{aligned}
 c_{1111} &= \frac{1}{6} \tilde{a}_{11111} + 4(\tilde{a}_{21111} + \tilde{a}_{31111} + \tilde{a}_{41111}), \\
 c_{2222} &= \frac{1}{6} \tilde{a}_{12222} + 4(\tilde{a}_{22222} + \tilde{a}_{32222} + \tilde{a}_{42222}), \\
 c_{1112} &= \frac{1}{24} (\tilde{a}_{11112} + \tilde{a}_{11121} + \tilde{a}_{11211} + \tilde{a}_{12111}) + \tilde{a}_{21112} + \tilde{a}_{21121} + \tilde{a}_{31112}, \\
 c_{1222} &= \frac{1}{24} (\tilde{a}_{11222} + \tilde{a}_{12122} + \tilde{a}_{12212} + \tilde{a}_{12221}) + \tilde{a}_{22212} + \tilde{a}_{22221} + \tilde{a}_{32221}, \\
 c_{1122} &= \frac{1}{36} (\tilde{a}_{11122} + \tilde{a}_{11212} + \tilde{a}_{11221} + \tilde{a}_{12112} + \tilde{a}_{12121} + \tilde{a}_{12211}) \\
 &\quad + \frac{2}{3} (\tilde{a}_{21122} + \tilde{a}_{22211} + \tilde{a}_{41122} + \tilde{a}_{42211}), \\
 c_{6611} &= \frac{1}{2} (\tilde{a}_{21211} + \tilde{a}_{22111} + \tilde{a}_{31121} + \tilde{a}_{31211} + \tilde{a}_{32111}) \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{2} (\tilde{a}_{41112} + \tilde{a}_{41121} + \tilde{a}_{41211} + \tilde{a}_{42111}), \\
 c_{6622} &= \frac{1}{2} (\tilde{a}_{21222} + \tilde{a}_{22122} + \tilde{a}_{31222} + \tilde{a}_{32122} + \tilde{a}_{32212}) \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{2} (\tilde{a}_{41222} + \tilde{a}_{42122} + \tilde{a}_{42212} + \tilde{a}_{42221}), \\
 c_{6612} &= \frac{1}{4} (\tilde{a}_{21212} + \tilde{a}_{21221} + \tilde{a}_{22112} + \tilde{a}_{22121}) \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{4} (\tilde{a}_{31122} + \tilde{a}_{31212} + \tilde{a}_{31221} + \tilde{a}_{32112} + \tilde{a}_{32121} + \tilde{a}_{32211}), \\
 c_{6666} &= \frac{1}{4} (\tilde{a}_{41212} + \tilde{a}_{41221} + \tilde{a}_{42112} + \tilde{a}_{42121}).
 \end{aligned}$$

B. Derivatives of Some Tensor Functions

The following table summarises the tensor functions and respective derivatives that are useful for arriving at the derivative of the strain-energy function expressed by (65).

Table 1: Derivatives of tensor functions appearing in the Strain-Energy function for arbitrary second-order tensors \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{L}_i , \mathbf{L}_j , \mathbf{L}_k and for any positive integer n .

$f(\mathbf{A})$	$df(\mathbf{A})/d\mathbf{A}$
$\text{tr}\mathbf{A}^n$	$n(\mathbf{A}^{n-1})^T$
$\text{tr}(\mathbf{A}^n \cdot \mathbf{L})$	$\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (\mathbf{A}^i \cdot \mathbf{L} \cdot \mathbf{A}^{n-1-i})^T$
$\text{tr}(\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{L}_i \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{L}_j)$	$(\mathbf{L}_i \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{L}_j + \mathbf{L}_j \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{L}_i)^T$
$\text{tr}(\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{L}_i \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{L}_j \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{L}_k)$	$(\mathbf{L}_i \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{L}_j \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{L}_k$ $+ \mathbf{L}_j \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{L}_k \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{L}_i$ $+ \mathbf{L}_k \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{L}_i \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{L}_j)^T$

References

- [1] C. Lopes, P. Camanho, Z. Gürdal, B. Tatting, Progressive failure analysis of tow-placed, variable-stiffness composite panels, *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 44 (2007) 8493–8516.
- [2] D. Jegley, B. Tatting, Z. Gürdal, Optimization of elastically tailored tow placed plates with holes, in: *Proceedings of the 44th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference*, Norfolk, VA, 2003.
- [3] S.-Y. Luo, 1.22 - finite elastic deformation, in: E. in Chief: Anthony Kelly, C. Zweben (Eds.), *Comprehensive Composite Materials*, Pergamon, Oxford, 2000, pp. 683 – 718.
- [4] Z. Gürdal, R. Olmedo, Composite laminates with spatially varying fiber orientations: Variable stiffness panel concept, in: *Proceedings of the 33rd AIAA/ASME/ASCE/ AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference*, Dallas, TX, 1992, pp. 798–808.
- [5] Z. Gürdal, R. Olmedo, In-plane response of laminates with spatially varying fiber orientations: Variable stiffness concept, *AIAA* 31 (1993) 751–758.
- [6] R. Olmedo, Z. Gürdal, Buckling response of laminates with spatially varying fiber orientations, in: *Proceedings of the 34th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference*, La Jolla, CA, 1993, pp. 2261–2269.
- [7] C. J. Waldhart, *Analysis of Tow-Placed, Variable-Stiffness Laminates*, Master's thesis, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, Blacksburg, VA, 1996.
- [8] C. Sousa, P. Camanho, A. Suleman, Analysis of multistable variable stiffness composite plates, *Composite Structures* 98 (2013) 34–46.
- [9] G. Indelicato, A. Albano, Symmetry properties of the elastic energy of a woven fabric with bending and twisting resistance, *Journal of Elasticity* 94 (2009) 33–54.
- [10] Z. Quanshui, J. Boehler, Tensor function representations as applied to formulating constitutive laws for clinotropic materials, *Acta Mechanica Sinica* 10 (1994) 336–348.
- [11] Q. Zheng, Theory of representations for tensor functions - a unified invariant approach to constitutive equations, *Applied Mechanics Reviews* 47 (1994) 545–587.
- [12] M. Itskov, *Tensor Algebra and Tensor Analysis for Engineers: With Applications to Continuum Mechanics*, 3rd ed., Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 2013.
- [13] G. A. Holzapfel, *Nonlinear Solid Mechanics: A Continuum Approach for Engineering*, John Wiley & Sons Ltd, West Sussex, 2000.
- [14] F. D. Murnaghan, Finite deformations of an elastic solid, *American Journal of Mathematics* 59 (1937) 235–260.
- [15] A. I. Lurie, *Nonlinear Theory of Elasticity*, North-Holland, Amsterdam, 1990.
- [16] A. V. Porubov, Amplification of nonlinear strain waves in solids. series on stability, vibration and control of systems, series a, *World Scientific* 9 (2003) 1–211.
- [17] M. Itskov, A generalized orthotropic hyperelastic material model with application to incompressible shells, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering* 50 (2001) 1777–1799.
- [18] Y. Başar, M. Itskov, A. Eckstein, Composite laminates: nonlinear interlaminar stress analysis by multi-layer shell elements, *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 185 (2000) 367–397.

- [19] H. T. Hahn, S. W. Tsai, Nonlinear elastic behavior of unidirectional composite laminae, *Journal of Composite Materials* 7 (1973) 102–118.